

Analysis Strategy Management: Implementation Planning, Organizing, Evaluating and Leadership Style

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to look at existing literacies with existing findings by supporting or looking at their implementation in a research result in the paper. This paper uses a qualitative approach by finding findings that are implemented. Literacy comes from journals with papers related to the topic, the implementation of the findings of this topic is evidenced in this paper. Various fields in the objects found from various existing paper literature such as strategy management used by all fields based on the papers found, Planning with a variety of planning models that are according to the theory used by researchers in the papers found, Organizing an organization in various fields is needed and with a variety of models, Evaluating in organizations implemented by all organizations with how management in running and Leadership Style used. Mostly in the findings of this paper are transformational leadership and transactional leadership. This paper makes a contribution and takes a role in the results by using a literature review of various paper findings

INTRODUCTION

In an ever-changing business and organizational environment, strategic management plays a central role as a guarantor of long-term growth and prosperity. According to (David & David, 2017) examines the important elements of strategic management, with special attention to implementation planning, organizational structure, evaluation, and leadership style, and how they are related to achieving organizational goals. Strategic management analysis is a procedure that includes planning, organizing, evaluating and managing. Although there are no exact search results directly related to this topic, we can gain knowledge from related literature. For example, reflective practice has emerged as an important part of teachers' professional growth, providing opportunities for teachers to reflect on their teaching methods, including classroom management, teaching strategies, teaching materials and student learning challenges (Tosriadi et al., 2018).

Strategic management relies on the interaction of implementation planning, organization, evaluation and management style. These components do not work in isolation, but rather influence and affect each other (Woodside & LaPlaca, 2014). Organizations that understand the importance of harmoniously combining these components will be better equipped to skillfully navigate the complexities of the business world. A well-executed strategic management process ensures that an organization not only develops effective strategies, but is also able to implement them, skillfully adapt to changing circumstances, and continuously strive to improve its strategic capabilities, ultimately culminating in sustainable growth and competitive development (Powell, 2014).

According to (Hitt & Duane Ireland, 2017) Implementation planning acts as a bridge between strategic vision and concrete implementation. It involves carefully translating strategic objectives into actionable plans and tasks. The prerequisites for successful implementation planning are a clear understanding of the organization's capabilities, well-thought-out resource allocation, and the creation of clear timelines. It serves as a blueprint that guides resource allocation, accountability, and tracks progress toward strategic goals (Hitt & Duane Ireland, 2017). Organizing is the art of organizing an organization to facilitate the smooth execution of its strategic plan. This includes outlining roles and responsibilities, creating a hierarchical structure and establishing effective communication channels (Koseoglu, 2016). In accordance with the chosen strategy, there is a planned organizational structure that enables effective coordination between teams and departments. In addition, the study also considered key aspects such as delegation and empowerment, both of which are essential for agility and adaptability in today's dynamic business environment.

The evaluation process is more than just financial indicators, it extends to quality dimensions such as customer satisfaction, employee engagement, and market share. A robust evaluation mechanism enables the organization to identify areas that require improvement and facilitates the necessary course corrections in strategic efforts. Management style is the foundation for the development of strategic management in an organization. Different situations may require different leadership styles, ranging from autocratic to democratic,

transactional to transformational. Effective leaders adapt their style to meet organizational goals and the changing needs of the team. Leadership that fosters open communication, empowers employees and encourages innovation can significantly influence the outcome of strategic initiatives. The purpose of this paper is to look at existing literacies with existing findings by supporting or looking at their implementation in a research result in the paper.

REVIEW

Strategy Management

According to (Yunus, 2016) the term strategic management comes from two words. Strategic comes from the Greek word strategy which means the art or science of being a general. An effective Greek general must lead his troops, win battles, defend his territory to protect his city from enemy attacks and defeat his enemy. The relatively broad definition of strategic management shows that strategic management is a system consisting of several components that are interrelated and move harmoniously towards the same direction. The first part of strategic management is strategic planning, which includes elements such as the organization's vision, mission, and strategic goals. The second component is operational implementation, which includes operational goals and objectives, management functions such as organization, implementation and budgeting, situational policies, internal and external network coordination, monitoring and evaluation functions, and feedback mechanisms.

Strategic management is the procedure by which strategies are designed and implemented to achieve organizational goals and objectives. It involves evaluating internal and external factors, setting goals, creating strategies, and allocating resources to achieve those goals. In the context of city government, the inclusion of sustainable development management in strategic planning can promote sustainability as a progressive initiative (Zeemering, 2018). Strategy development involves a combination of three main processes as follows (Yunus, 2016): 1) Conduct a situation analysis, self-assessment and competitor analysis both internally and externally in both micro and macro environments.; 2) These objectives should be parallel in both the short and long term. During this process, one should pay attention to the formulation of the vision (long-term perspective and future possibilities), the mission statement (which defines the role of the organization in the public environment), the general objectives of the organization (both financial and strategic) and the strategic objectives of the business unit (related to the objectives of the organization in achieving the expected goals).

Implementation Planning

According to (Smith et al., 2022) Implementation planning is the process of strategizing and organizing the actions needed to carry out a specific project or project. This includes identifying problems, determining different strategies, estimating resource requirements, and creating a project schedule. Implementation planning plays an important role in project management, which ensures that projects are completed on schedule, within budget constraints, and

achieve the desired quality criteria. For example, in the field of research and practical application, decision analysis can be used to strengthen the process of implementation planning.

Effective implementation planning is critical to the successful implementation of enterprise resource planning systems (Voronkova et al., 2017).

Implementation planning is an important part of strategic management. It involves the process of definition and strategic organization of the procedures required to carry out a specific project or initiative. Implementation planning includes the formulation of a theme, the creation of several plans, the estimation of resources, and the establishment of a project schedule. It acts as a safeguard to ensure that projects are completed quickly, within budget limits and according to established quality criteria. For example, in the field of research and practical application, decision analysis can be used to strengthen the implementation planning process. In the manufacturing sector, the effective implementation of enterprise resource planning systems relies heavily on well-structured implementation planning. Therefore, implementation planning remains a central and important part of strategic management, making a significant contribution to an organization's ability to achieve its goals and aspirations (Rentes et al., 2018; Yu, 2022).

Organizing

In the field of human resource management, the term "organization" refers to systematically organizing and structuring resources, tasks, and activities in a rational and efficient manner to achieve clear goals and objectives. Organizing is an important part of the field of human resource management and includes various functions (Safitri & Aslami, 2022). Organizing is an integral part of human resource management and plays a key role in achieving organizational goals. This is achieved by ensuring the effective and efficient organization and supervision of the workforce (Rahsel & Gumanti, 2022).

Organizing is an important part of human resource management and includes many tasks and activities such as; 1) It involves identifying the tasks, duties and responsibilities associated with a particular job, : 2) It involves structuring jobs in a way that maximizes efficiency and productivity,; 3) It involves forecasting future manpower needs and developing plans to meet those needs,; 4) It involves identifying and attracting qualified candidates for open positions,; 5) It means providing employees with the knowledge and skills they need to do their jobs effectively,; 6) It includes setting performance goals, providing feedback, and evaluating employee performance,; 7) It means developing and administering competitive and fair compensation and benefits programs.

Evaluating

According to (Sari, 2020) Appraisal means the process of measuring and evaluating employee performance and the effectiveness of HR policies and practices, Appraisal is an important part of human resource management and includes a number of functions, including: 1) involves evaluating employee

performance based on predetermined goals and objectives, ; 2) provides feedback to employees regarding their performance and guides them to improve their skills and abilities, ; 3) involves evaluating the effectiveness of training programs in terms of improving employee performance and achieving organizational goals, ; 4) evaluates the effectiveness of HR policies and practices in achieving organizational goals and meeting employee needs, ; 5) measures employee satisfaction, motivation, and commitment to the organization.

Leadership Style

Leadership style refers to how a leader approaches the task of directing, motivating and leading his or her team or organization. Different leadership styles can affect employee performance, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance in different ways (Likdanawati et al., 2022). Leadership styles and their impact on performance in different contexts; 1) Transactional Leadership Style, This approach involves inspiring and motivating employees to reach their full potential and align with common goals. Research shows that transformational leadership has a positive impact on employee performance in various sectors, including education, health, and public administration.; 2) Democratic Leadership Style, This management style involves employees in the decision-making process and encourages open communication and collaboration. Research shows that democratic leadership can have a positive impact on job satisfaction and employee performance in areas such as education and healthcare; 3) Leadership Style Autocratic leadership: This approach involves making decisions without seeking input from employees and relying on authority and control to motivate the workforce. While autocratic leadership may be effective in certain situations, such as crises or military operations, it may fail to increase employee engagement or job satisfaction, ; 4) Autocratic leadership, this approach involves making decisions without seeking input from employees and relying on authority and control to motivate the workforce. While autocratic leadership may be effective in certain situations, such as crises or military operations, it may fail to increase employee engagement or job satisfaction, 5) Charismatic leadership: This style revolves around inspiring and motivating employees through the leader's personality and vision. While charismatic leadership may be effective in certain scenarios, such as startups or creative industries, it may not be able to ensure long-term organizational stability.

METHODOLOGY

This paper uses a qualitative approach by finding findings that are implemented. Literacy is derived from journals with papers related to the topic, the implementation of the findings of this topic is evidenced in this paper.

RESULTS

The results of this paper come from the literature that contains papers related to the implementation of the variables in this paper which starts from a study belonging to (Stoyanova, 2018) stating Dynamic Capabilities and Strategic Management "is an innovative business publication that provides a brief and

comprehensive analysis of dynamic capabilities. It delves into their core concepts and explores the strategic importance they offer to researchers and practitioners in the fields of business strategy, innovation, entrepreneurship and economics, then the study from (Johnsen, 2015) states that strategic management in the public sector is largely based on strategic planning, often combined with other strategic management approaches, although there are trends in contemporary strategic management theory, reducing formal, mechanical design. According to study by (Vishnevskiy et al., 2016) in their paper on strategic management suggests a new integrated action plan that harmonizes these two perspectives. It is oriented towards the strategic planning of both businesses and state institutions, while keeping in mind the long-term goals of social and economic development, it opens up alternative options for choosing the most efficient resource allocation. The unified roadmap covers various stages of potential innovation development, including current stages of the innovation value chain such as research and development, manufacturing, market entry, services and market expansion, as well as future stages of new technologies, products and services.

The study from (Hagermoser Sanetti et al., 2018) in their paper states the effectiveness of implementation planning, strategies that include logistical action implementation planning and identifying implementation barriers, and strategies that include participatory modeling, didactic and in-life interventions, evidence-based practical implementation by teachers, teacher engagement and quality improved along with implementation design and participant modeling, but these improvements were not fully maintained after 1 and 2 months of follow-up. A similar pattern was also seen in students' disruptive behavior.

The study from (Kools & George, 2020) states in their paper strategic planning for the future, it also fulfills public responsibility and allows customers and other stakeholders to participate in the development and promotion of public services. However, there are also unintended consequences. The study from (Smith et al., 2022) states the use of decision analysis in implementation planning, application of model thinking, making a business case for analyzing decisions; determining when, how and to whom decision analysis is more or less useful; improving reporting and transparency of cost information; and increasing collaboration and training opportunities.

The study from (Aracıoğlu et al., 2013) states that performance measurement has become a popular concept in strategic management, and managers to improve production processes. A further study from (Kohl et al., 2016) states in their paper that developing an integrated evaluation method that can manage the life cycle of innovation initiatives on an ongoing basis in terms of implementation progress and effectiveness. The evaluation system follows a multidimensional approach involving internal and external stakeholders, applying a combination of evaluation tools, including key performance indicators, evaluation and self-review procedures, and monitoring and reporting tools. The most important output of the evaluation system can be derived from improvement proposals and specific action plans, which can be used to respond quickly to potential challenges.

Program and policy evaluation is an important part of strategic management. Managers and other managers need to know "what works" to determine if strategic priorities are being met, Managers should be aware of alternative approaches to evaluating programs and policies to ensure that the methods can capture the complexity of social phenomena inherent in each program and policy (Camerong, 2014). cost, interoperability, and scalability are the most important FPVs for energy cloud deployment, to determine the strategic direction in management as well as how to carry out evaluation after deployment (Schaefer et al., 2021).

Transformational and transactional leadership styles positively and statistically significantly predict subordinates' extra effort, perceived leadership effectiveness, and satisfaction with the leader. Manager training is beneficial to the stability and sustainability of sports clubs (Martínez-Moreno et al., 2021). A small contribution to this area of research examines the relationship between strategic management processes and leadership personality (Stephanie Slater, CardiffBusiness School, U.K., 2015).

DISCUSSION

The literature found on implementation related to the topic in this paper is dozens, representing each of the variables in this paper, in general implementation is represented from the papers found and used in this paper from the last ten years.

Specifically, the variables in this paper support the implementation of the papers used and the results found in the papers with different objects..

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Various fields in the objects found from various existing literature papers such as strategy management used by all fields based on the papers found, Planning with a variety of planning models according to the theory used by researchers in the papers found, Organizing an organization in various fields is needed and with a variety of models, Evaluating in organizations carried out by all organizations with how management is running and Leadership Style used Most of the findings in this paper are transformational leadership and transactional leadership.

This paper makes a contribution and takes a role in the results by using a literature review of various paper findings.

FURTHER STUDY

The implications of the results of this paper are to be continued by other researchers with the variables in this paper or the same with various research objects.

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